

Orbit Selection for Earth Observation Missions using a Tradespace Exploration Approach: a pilot study ^{*}

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Summary: Orbit selection for satellite missions is a process rather than a set of explicit calculations. The general orbit selection process has a few steps. First, establishing orbit type, orbit-related mission requirements and orbit performance, evaluating orbit performance for many candidates, performing orbit trades, and selecting several optimal design alternatives. The selection process could be clear, as many design candidates exit, and usually, the answer is several different credible orbits rather than a single answer. Finding such orbits is a complex task since the orbit candidates are represented by a multi-dimensional table containing numerous orbit parameters and many performance-related figures of merit, and most candidates achieve comparable performance. Therefore, a decision-making support method is required to aid the designers in discovering the optimal solutions. This study investigates the utility of Tradespace exploration in orbit selection. As proof of concept, a pilot study was conducted on the orbit data from the Satellite Cross-Calibration Radiometer (SCR) series Pre-Phase A Study Report. The principal component analysis (PCA) provides a clear visualisation of all design alternatives, and Pareto optimisation can identify the optimal orbits. Moreover, using clustering analysis enables the discovery of hidden design patterns. The pilot study demonstrates that tradespace exploration is a promising method for supporting faster, more accurate, and more reliable orbit selection.

Keywords: Tradespace exploration, orbit selection, Earth observation satellite mission design.

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Introduction

In the early design phase of any space mission, orbit selection is a fundamental process for all space mission design. In practice, orbit selection for a space mission is a process rather than a set of explicit calculations. The general orbit selection process has a few steps. Take the previous study in [2] for example. The first step is establishing orbit type, orbit-related mission requirements and orbit performance; the second step is evaluating orbit performance for many candidates based on orbit simulation; the final step is performing orbit trades by manual comparison to select several optimal design alternatives. However, the manual comparison makes “finding such orbits is a complex task since most candidates achieve comparable performance, making it difficult to pick up the recommended orbits by inspection”[2]. This is because the orbit candidates are represented by a multi-dimensional table containing numerous orbit parameters and many performance-related figures of merit. And there is normally more than one selection criterion in which performance looks similar. Therefore, a tool for supporting orbit experts /designers in selecting the recommended orbits is needed to make decisions effectively and efficiently.

Our previous work [1] proved that a combinatorial approach to Tradespace exploration could find such optimal designs for CubeSat architectures and be useful for reducing decision-makers’ cognitive workload when designing CubeSats. This motivates this study to investigate the feasibility of Tradespace exploration as a tool to help orbit selection decision-making. As an initial proof of concept, a pilot study is conducted on the Satellite Cross-calibration Radiometer (SCR) series mission, which forms part of Australia’s contribution to the global observing system. The differences are that the previous work is using simulated artificial data where the problem and objective function are well developed. However, the case study is a real-world scenario and the objective where and the objectives are defined clearly, while the case study is a real-world scenario and did not provide clear selection criteria, such as maximising or minimising certain objectives. Second, the optimisation objective is not clearly defined. In addition, there is no predetermined answer in the typical tradespace exploitation assumption. However, since the recommended orbits have already been selected in the SCR report [2], the previous algorithm is tailored to an assurance problem, implying that the case study includes human interaction. The interaction includes interesting the resulting solution and evaluating the solution with the report writers.

This study explores applying the existing algorithm from our previous work [1] to a new problem. The algorithm integrates principal component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical clustering using Cosine as a distance metric. The PCA provides a clear visualisation of all design alternatives. Clustering analysis enables the discovery of hidden patterns that would otherwise be missed by human inspection analysis. Pareto optimisation is added in the process to determine the optimal orbits. The computer results coincide with the recommended orbits identified in the SCR report, which means the pilot study is successful. In addition, throughout the study, insights are acquired into translating designers’ ambiguous selection criteria, such as maximising every objective simultaneously, into well-defined selection goals that can be effectively utilised in setting up the trade space exploration case study. The pilot demonstrates that tradespace exploration is a powerful data-driven aid to decision-making for orbit selection in practice. In addition, Tradespace exploration can provide domain experts with additional assurance that their recommended orbit candidates are the most efficient solution.

Since the focus is on the application, a brief explanation of the approach is given. The focus will be on the experiment setup and how the previous algorithm be tailored for this specific application. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II introduces the study

case. Section III presents the problem formulation derived from the relevant work. Section VI presents and interprets the results. Section V draws some conclusions, limitations and future work of the study.

Study case

This section briefly introduces the background of the study case as the input data is derived from the orbit selection part in the SCR report. Details of the orbit selection process can be found in the SCR report.

The SCR report is a pre-phase A study for an Australian Satellite Cross-Calibration Radiometer mission published by the Australian National Concurrent Design Facility (ANCDF). The motivation is that Australia’s reliance on EO data has never been more profound, with up to \$2.5 billion in economic benefits in 2020[3]. Australia aims to build sovereign capabilities, triple the size of the space sector by 2030 and engage in more domestic and international partnerships and agreements. This SCR report explores opportunities for uplifting Australian capability and contributing to the US land imaging program while improving the calibration of the optical satellites. According to the requirements, the Australian Satellite Cross-Calibration Radiometer (SCR) series of hyperspectral sensors are proposed. Also, SCR satellites would be launched into orbits that would provide coincident imagery opportunities with several highly calibrated Earth Observation missions such as the NASA/USGS Landsat, and EC (European Commission) Sentinel.

The primary target orbits for the SCR mission are Landsat-8, Sentinel-2A and 2B. Since these three target orbits are all sun-synchronous repeating orbits, the report has proposed 32 orbit candidates which are also sun-synchronous orbits. The proposed 32 orbits are given in Table 1 derived from Table 24 in the SCR report. Each orbit candidate has eight features, from Alt(km) in column 3, to Min FOV (deg) in column 10.

Table 1 Candidate orbits summary derived from Table 24 in the SCR report[2]

Mission	NORAD	Alt (km)	v_o (revs/day)	D_{T_o} (revs)	C_{T_o} (days)	N_{T_o} (revs)	E_{T_o} (days)	Min. Swath (km)	Min. FOV (deg)
Landsat-8	39084	699.57	15	-7	16	233	7	172.00	14.00
Sentinel-2A	40697	786.13	14	3	10	143	3	280.24	20.17
Sentinel-2B	42063								
Candidate	10001	503.64	15	3	16	243	5	164.92	18.58
Candidate	10002	466.05	15	5	16	245	3	163.57	19.88
Candidate	10003	515.01	15	3	20	303	7	132.26	14.62
Candidate	10004	454.88	15	7	20	307	3	130.54	16.32
Candidate	10005	425.30	15	9	20	309	9	129.69	17.33
Candidate	10006	492.31	15	9	40	609	9	65.80	7.65
Candidate	10007	477.27	15	11	40	611	11	65.59	7.86
Candidate	10008	462.32	15	13	40	613	3	65.38	8.09
Candidate	10009	432.66	15	17	40	617	7	64.95	8.58
Candidate	10010	417.95	15	19	40	619	19	64.74	8.86
Candidate	10011	403.32	16	-19	40	621	19	64.53	9.15
Candidate	10012	584.27	15	-3	40	597	13	67.13	6.57
Candidate	10013	537.91	15	3	40	603	13	66.46	7.07
Candidate	10014	507.42	15	7	40	607	17	66.02	7.44
Candidate	10015	619.55	15	-3	16	237	5	169.09	15.53
Candidate	10016	607.74	15	-3	20	297	7	134.93	12.66
Candidate	10017	631.41	15	-9	40	591	9	67.81	6.15
Candidate	10018	615.61	15	-7	40	593	17	67.58	6.28
Candidate	10019	645.98	15	-13	48	707	11	56.68	5.02
Candidate	10020	632.73	15	-11	48	709	13	56.52	5.11
Candidate	10021	606.43	15	-7	48	713	7	56.21	5.31
Candidate	10022	593.37	15	-5	48	715	19	56.05	5.41
Candidate	10023	588.72	15	-5	56	835	11	47.99	4.67
Candidate	10024	577.60	15	-3	56	837	19	47.88	4.75
Candidate	10025	645.03	15	-15	56	825	15	48.58	4.31
Candidate	10026	633.68	15	-13	56	827	13	48.46	4.38
Candidate	10027	622.37	15	-11	56	829	5	48.34	4.45
Candidate	10028	611.11	15	-9	56	831	25	48.23	4.52
Candidate	10029	628.77	15	-13	60	887	23	45.18	4.11
Candidate	10030	649.96	15	-17	60	883	7	45.39	4.00
Candidate	10031	618.24	15	-11	60	889	11	45.08	4.18
Candidate	10032	597.29	15	-7	60	893	17	44.88	4.30

Table 2 Triple coincidence results of the 32 orbit candidates derived from Table 25 from the SCR report [2].

Table 25 Triple Coincidence Results

Object ID	Altitude (km)	C_{To} (days)	Overall			Over Land		
			Total WRS2 Bins	Unique WRS2 Bin	Average Overlap (km)	Total WRS2 Bins	Unique WRS2 Bin	Average Overlap (km)
10001	503.64	16	61198	13797/28426	45.68	17067	4408/6954	45.55
10002	466.05	16	59850	14250/28426	42.81	17990	4969/6954	42.17
10003	515.01	20	61651	14085/28426	46.20	18032	4760/6954	45.97
10004	454.88	20	59106	13764/28426	42.12	17440	4649/6954	42.05
10005	425.30	20	56987	12657/28426	39.77	17037	4322/6954	39.54
10006	492.31	40	61013	14195/28426	44.85	18221	4913/6954	44.51
10007	477.27	40	60380	13298/28426	43.71	17753	4666/6954	43.40
10008	462.32	40	60219	13746/28426	42.66	17993	4773/6954	43.01
10009	432.66	40	57806	12645/28426	40.32	17229	4289/6954	39.91
10010	417.95	40	56753	11107/28426	39.22	17307	3915/6954	39.20
10011	403.32	40	55425	12371/28426	38.08	16131	4233/6954	37.70
10012	584.27	40	61966	14600/28426	50.59	17577	4755/6954	50.27
10013	537.91	40	63017	14338/28426	48.02	18456	4902/6954	47.89
10014	507.42	40	61950	12177/28426	45.83	18281	4213/6954	45.75
10015	619.55	16	61828	14979/28426	52.29	17669	4808/6954	51.95
10016	607.74	20	61999	15762/28426	51.67	17916	5122/6954	51.67
10017	631.41	40	60501	13291/28426	52.53	17393	4477/6954	51.92
10018	615.61	40	61437	15354/28426	52.29	17704	5057/6954	52.20
10019	645.98	48	60625	15277/28426	53.23	17382	5001/6954	53.29
10020	632.73	48	60606	15957/28426	52.55	17506	5276/6954	52.55
10021	606.43	48	61956	14488/28426	51.88	18017	4802/6954	51.94
10022	593.37	48	62289	16004/28426	50.98	18199	5291/6954	50.16
10023	588.72	56	61644	12466/28426	50.94	17823	4262/6954	50.87
10024	577.60	56	62321	15658/28426	50.07	18250	4955/6954	49.90
10025	645.03	56	60833	13061/28426	53.01	17294	4268/6954	52.39
10026	633.68	56	60639	14611/28426	52.78	17616	5076/6954	53.08
10027	622.37	56	61791	14048/28426	52.68	17892	4571/6954	52.56
10028	611.11	56	62106	16159/28426	51.83	17553	5408/6954	52.63
10029	628.77	60	59970	13027/28426	51.77	17097	4293/6954	51.38
10030	649.96	60	60415	15457/28426	53.68	17583	5131/6954	53.63
10031	618.24	60	61545	15037/28426	52.36	17783	4979/6954	53.04
10032	597.29	60	62071	15115/28426	51.29	18222	5143/6954	50.83

Then, the orbit experts calculated the triple coincidence which is the coverage of each orbit (see Table 2). The performance is not a single but six features, from column 4 “Overall Total WRS2 Bins” to column 9 “Over Land Average Overlap (km)”. The selection criteria are to maximise the coincident data collection opportunities between SCR and the target orbits. In the SCR report, three candidates highlighted in yellow are selected by orbit experts as the recommended orbits. And the selection criterion is not as definite as it generally means to the maximum of all the six coverage criteria.

As the SCR report [2] stated, “most of the orbits achieve similar performance in terms of coincident data collection opportunities”. Therefore “identifying such an orbit is a moderately complex task”. In this context, "similar performance" can be understood as the absence of a single solution that optimises all objectives simultaneously. For instance, in Table 2, it can be seen that Object 10001 performs better than Object 10002 in columns 4, 6, and 9, but not in all other columns. Thus, a computer-aided tool to support decision-making is needed.

Tradespace Exploration problem setting

In concurrent engineering environments, it may require several formal sessions taking weeks/months to examine a sufficient range of Tradespace for the customer to make well-informed programmatic decisions. Customers that conducted tradespace exploration studies benefited from the rapid identification of optimum candidate solutions from a large tradespace in less than a day[4]. The Tradespace exploration approach is rooted in computer-based algorithms. Thus, this approach saves the designers both time and money so they can focus more on detailed concurrent engineering sessions rather than comparison and selection.

Tradespace

A tradespace is the potential solution space, usually stored in databases consisting of a set of multiple design alternatives, data attributes, and system parameters [5]. From Table 3, it can be seen that the tradespace is an array of numbers, where n is the number of design alternatives (here are the orbit candidates and $n=32$). Each candidate has multiple features /dimensions/variables.

Table 3 Coordinates in the design space and in the objective space

	Design space			Objective space		
Variables	Design variables			Objective variables		
	d_1	...	d_m	Obj_1	...	Obj_k
Design alternative 1						
⋮						
Design alternative n						

Typically, the exploration approach includes two basic steps. The first step is to generate thousands (or more) of simulated design alternatives by varying design variables and storing the corresponding values of the performance variables for each alternative [1]. However, the step can be omitted as we can use Table 1 and Table 2 to form the data in design and objective space, respectively. Specifically, the data in the design space is a 32 by 8 matrix with eight features. The first six are orbit parameters, and the last two features (Min Swath and Min FOV) are payload parameters. The data in the object space is a 32 by 6 matrix with 6 coverage performance metrics. The first three are overall, and the last three are over land.

The second step is visualising the orbit candidates, revealing the design patterns and finding the best solutions with Pareto optimisation [1][6]. This combinational approach is shown in Figure 1. Firstly, PCA reduces the number of dimensions; secondly, hierarchical cosine clustering reveals hidden patterns. Then, results are visualised on two-dimensional graphs with the principal components as axes. Finally, Pareto optimisation is applied to find the best options. The visualisation is shown to the orbit experts, and final solutions can be made with human interactions. In this case study, the algorithm identified six optimal designs, but only three of them were chosen as the recommended orbits based on input and feedback from the experts.

Figure 1 Flowchart of the combinational tradespace exploration approach (modified from our previous work in [1])

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA is a classical multivariate statistical technique widely used by applied research[7]. It was pioneered in 1891 by Karl Person, as a way of adjusting planes via orthogonal least squares and developed further in 1993 by Harold Hotelling in covariance and correlation analysis[8]. Nowadays, PCA is one of the most widely used techniques, especially in those fields that deal with large data sets, where a dimensionality reduction is sought [9]. There is a relationship between variance and information, the larger the variance carried by a line, the larger the dispersion of the data points along it. The dispersion along the line is proportional to the information it has [10].

We use PCA to re-express a data set in a 2-dimensional pictorial representation, increasing the interpretability while minimising information loss. This is achieved by creating ‘summary’ indexes of variance for the dataset. Each index is known as a principal component (PC) and is desired to have a large amount of variance. The PCs are new variables that are uncorrelated and maximise variance. PCA represents the multivariate dataset with a biplot [11]. If two orbit candidates are identical, they will be the same dots in the biplot.

Hierarchical Clustering

Clustering analysis is a computer-oriented data analysis technique called unsupervised learning in pattern recognition [12]. The problem of clustering analysis is to divide a set of samples into homogeneous groups. Then, the features pertaining to the samples are used in clustering analysis to calculate the similarity between the samples. In this study, the agglomerative hierarchical clustering is used. Agglomerative hierarchical clustering builds a hierarchy structure of clusters by merging all objects, producing a single, all-inclusive cluster at the top, and singleton clusters of individual objects at the bottom [13].

The input data for clustering is standardised data in the design space, as the raw data has different units. After standardisation, the new data are centred on having a mean 0 and scaled to have a standard deviation of 1. The number of clusters is set to 2 directly as two sets of orbit candidates are considered in the SCR report (page 152). One is an orbit candidate whose minimum swath width is equivalent to the minimum FOV, and another set of orbit candidates has longer repeat cycles.

Pareto optimisation

The general definition of a Pareto optimisation (also termed multi-objective optimisation) [14] is shown in Equation (1).

$$\min F(x) \\ F(x) = (f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_k(x)) \text{ subject to } x \in S \quad (1)$$

Where the number of the objective function is k , S is the feasible region for the decision vectors x and $f_i(x)$ is a scalar objective function, with $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. Though the minimisation problems are considered from the above equation, this does not limit the generality of the produced results. For example, maximisation of an objective function f_i is the same as minimisation of $-f_i$.

The selection criteria in this study case are to maximise all six coverage metrics. After PCA, the six metrics are reduced to two dimensions: PC1 and PC2. The original multiple-objective optimal problem is transformed into a bi-objective problem. Maximising the original six metrics is equivalent to maximising PC1 and minimum PC2. The Pareto front will be located at the bottom right of the plots.

Results

In this part, it is shown how the suggested approach can help with orbit selection issues. The focus is on interpreting and gaining new knowledge from the results.

Biplot of the design and objective space

PCA provides information about the proportion of variance explained by each principal component. By examining the cumulative explained variance, we can determine if the retained principal components capture a significant portion of the total variance in the original dataset. A higher cumulative explained variance suggests that the reduced-dimensional data retains substantial information from the original datasets. The overall variance experienced in each principal component for the design and objective space is illustrated in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. The bar charts help understand the difference in magnitudes, noting that PC1 represents most of the dataset. The first two principal components have explained 77.9% and 77.1% variability for the data in design and objective space, respectively. The values mean it is reasonable to reduce the dimensions to 2D.

Then, the 32 orbit candidates in design and objective space are plotted in a lower 2D space in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. The first two principal components define a coordinate system of orthogonal axes in these two plots. Each dot presents an orbit candidate, and the NOARD ID is marked near this dot.

Figure 2 Variance in principal components for data in the design space

Figure 3 Variance in principal components for data in the objective space

Figure 4 2D representation of orbit candidates in design space before clustering

Figure 5 2D representation of orbit candidates in objective space before clustering

Clustering results and Optimal solutions

As the SCR report considered two generic options for defining mission orbits [2], we cluster the 32 orbit candidates into two groups. In Figure 6, the two clusters are represented by different colours, blue for Cluster 1 and red for Cluster 2. Then we use the obtained segmentation results to colour the corresponding design points in objective space, see Figure 7.

Figure 6 2D representation of orbit candidates in design space after clustering

Figure 7 2D representation of orbit candidates in objective space after clustering

Then, the Pareto optimal solutions are identified on the bottom right of the plots in Figure 7, denoted with “+”. The six optimal orbit candidates are NORAD ID 10032, 10022, 10028, 10030, 10019, and 10029. Back to the design space, we also mark the optimal solutions with “+”. It can be found that all the optimal solutions are blue dots in Cluster 1. This reveals some unseen design “bias” as all the recommended solutions belong to one set of orbits. The results help designers know what type of orbits they will seek. Suppose designers want to look further for the optimal orbit design. In that case, they need to add more candidates in the preferred type of orbit.

Human-computer interactions

The three expert-recommended orbits in the SCR report [2] are highlighted in yellow, and the six optimal orbits obtained by our algorithm are indicated by red arrows in Figure 8 (bottom

half of Table 2). The report was already available when the pilot research was carried out. The authors discussed the findings of this investigation with the orbit specialists who authored the SCR report.

First, the outcomes of the computer selection incorporate the outcomes of the human selection. Experts' feedback indicates that the outcomes boost their degree of decision-making confidence. Second, three orbits (10022, 10029, and 10032) are eliminated because of human factors. The expert-recommended orbits are dots near the knee area in the Pareto-optimal fronts (see Figure 7). It is easy to explain the difference from the perspective of the computer algorithm as solutions near the knee area offer a good compromise between conflicting objectives, often representing a desirable balance in the trade-offs. The specialists thought that the eliminated solutions could have had a higher favourable balance as they sacrificed too much for one particular objective. Third, if the specialists intend to expand the pool of orbit candidates, they will be advised to consider including more orbits from Cluster 1 (represented by blue dots). This approach may bring more dots near the knee area of the Pareto-optimal fronts' knee area. In that case, it is more likely that more preferred solutions can be discovered through the increased availability of orbit candidates. The counter-example is that it is not advised to continue increasing orbit candidates from Cluster 2.

10018	615.61	40	61437	15354/28426	52.29	17704	5057/6954	52.20
10019	645.98	48	60625	15277/28426	53.23	17382	5001/6954	53.29
10020	632.73	48	60606	15957/28426	52.55	17506	5276/6954	52.55
10021	606.43	48	61956	14488/28426	51.88	18017	4802/6954	51.94
10022	593.37	48	62289	16004/28426	50.98	18199	5291/6954	50.16
10023	588.72	56	61644	12466/28426	50.94	17823	4262/6954	50.87
10024	577.60	56	62321	15658/28426	50.07	18250	4955/6954	49.90
10025	645.03	56	60833	13061/28426	53.01	17294	4268/6954	52.39
10026	633.68	56	60639	14611/28426	52.78	17616	5076/6954	53.08
10027	622.37	56	61791	14048/28426	52.68	17892	4571/6954	52.56
10028	611.11	56	62106	16159/28426	51.83	17553	5408/6954	52.63
10029	628.77	60	59970	13027/28426	51.77	17097	4293/6954	51.38
10030	649.96	60	60415	15457/28426	53.68	17583	5131/6954	53.63
10031	618.24	60	61545	15037/28426	52.36	17783	4979/6954	53.04
10032	597.29	60	62071	15115/28426	51.29	18222	5143/6954	50.83

Figure 8 Comparison of algorithmically and expert-recommended orbits

Conclusion, limitation and Future Work

The purpose of this paper's pilot study was to employ tradespace exploration techniques to assist those who make decisions about the choice of orbits for space missions. This study created a visualisation tool to quickly determine the best candidates by evaluating the relationships between the applicants. We demonstrated how the suggested approach could help orbit specialists because it can quickly and precisely identify the best options while also exposing hidden design patterns. The use of machine learning algorithms to give computer-based decision support is demonstrated by the pilot project. According to the study, it is advantageous to utilise a Tradespace exploration technique when choosing optimal orbits for satellite missions since it allows for faster, more precise, and more dependable orbit selection. The research of the trade area can increase our self-assurance and reputation, mainly while conducting complicated trades.

The areas for improvement of the PCA approach are where the work is limited. The primary components do not explicitly specify which parameters the user should optimise for because they do not have defined meanings. To address this limitation, additional steps can be taken to enhance the interpretability and guidance provided by PCA. One approach is incorporating

domain knowledge or expert input to interpret and label the principal components based on their relevance to the specific problem or application. This can help establish a more meaningful connection between the principal components and the underlying parameters of interest. Furthermore, there needs to be more knowledge regarding the impact of the clustering approach utilised while analysing the design and goal space data. Although hierarchical cosine was employed in this experiment to produce two-dimensional visualisations, the advantages of using other clustering techniques have yet to be formally investigated.

The current study has a limited number of candidates. In future work, many orbit candidates can be created to be evaluated. In addition to the orbit selection problem, we are looking for more applications in the mission design. This strategy is anticipated to significantly advance the space mission systems engineering life cycle during the first stages of mission design.

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